

A Review on Modulation Techniques for EMI Mitigation on Machine Drives

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Abstract—As the electrical system in aircrafts scale-up in size, it becomes evermore challenging to compromise compatibility with high power density for EMI filters. In this paper, software mitigation techniques are explored. By exploiting inherent features of multilevel inverters, different modulation schemes are analysed and compared together with two new proposals. The outcome is a comprehensive trade-off under objective metrics also introduced in the paper.

Index Terms—Modulation, EMI, SVM, multilevel inverter, CMV.

I. INTRODUCTION

Commercial aerospace has been shifting towards more electric aircraft. Installed electric loads yield the replacement of the heavier legacy hydraulic/pneumatic systems while electrical hybridization of propulsion systems reduces fossil fuel consumption. Such initiatives result in a lighter aircraft and ultimately less CO₂ emissions [1]. However, the growth of the aircraft electrical network, now summing up to several megawatts, introduces new challenges in terms of electromagnetic interference (EMI).

EMI phenomenon is produced by the different sources of noise that can be found in an electrical system. Power converters are no exception to this rule. The operation of power electronics semiconductor switching devices produces voltages and currents rapidly changing (i.e., high dv/dt and di/dt). The voltage swings result in strong rapid changes of the electric fields that may disturb the environment, other devices or even sensor readings. The parasitic effects of circuits create fast charge changes on the circuit parasitic capacitances which produce current circulation on undesired circuit paths (e.g., common mode currents). In turn, the fast-switching currents will cause rapidly changing magnetic fields. The current regulation for aerospace applications, namely the DO-160G [2], differentiates between two types of EMI: conducted and radiated emissions.

Conducted emissions in power converters are generated by the circulation of undesired currents due to the noise generated by the switches as they interact with the different parasitic components of the system and the ground. The issues are caused by the fast switching of devices which is further aggravated when using wide-bandgap. A filter mitigating the noise generated at the input of the converter is required. In some cases, even at the output when connecting to very specific loads. In comparison to other regulations used for commercial equipment DO-160G does not make any distinction between common and differential mode. The objective for the designer is compliance with the mask, which measures the common mode component of the current.

Nonetheless, EMI filters add considerable volume and weight to the power converter, thus hindering the equipment's target metrics of power density and specific power. A common option to reduce EMI filters size is software-based mitigation. These solutions will focus on the application of different control and modulation schemes that could potentially reduce the amount of noise generated by the power converter. Specifically for machine drives, voltage source inverters (VSI) yield a wide variety of possibilities to accomplish noise mitigation through their modulation schemes.

This paper presents a comprehensive overview on the modulation challenges and intricacies for EMI mitigation as well as a literature review on different modulation techniques for common-mode (CM) noise mitigation. Simulation results are presented comparing literature modulation to two proposed schemes. The comparison is performed under objective metrics also defined in the paper.

II. MACHINE DRIVE MODULATION OVERVIEW

On a three-phase VSI the ac waveforms are synthesized by orderly alternating the input dc voltage sources among the output phases. A commonly deployed method to reproduce the desired output ac currents/voltages is the pulse width

modulation (PWM), where high-frequency pulses are generated containing the lower frequency ac signal modulated into the pulse's width. In the control system, the modulation block is responsible for converting the control output signals into temporized *on* and *off* switch states. Multilevel VSI topologies usually have extra degrees of freedom on their modulation, which can be used for further improvements of the system operation [3]. Fig. 1 depicts the full propulsion system including high-level the control/modulation block.

Fig. 1. Aircraft propulsion drive-train diagram with control system.

Different PWM strategies have been proposed in the literature. In [4] a comprehensive classification is presented. According to the authors, two main approaches can be followed when implementing the modulation technique for a given three-phase VSI: voltage-level- and space vector-based algorithms.

Techniques based on the voltage level commonly use one or more high-frequency carriers to generate PWM signals. The reference voltage levels coming from the control system are constantly compared in amplitude to the carrier, where the comparator's action qualifier can set the switch states to on or off depending on the operation results. On multilevel VSI topologies, multi-carrier approaches yield further optimization regarding carriers shift in amplitude, phase and shape. An analytical study on multi-carrier approaches is carried out in [5].

In space-vector modulation (SVM), the selection of the vectors, their deployment sequence, use of redundancies, operation axis-frame, among many other aspects are vast topics of research aiming to optimize the VSI operation [6]–[8]. While increasing complexity and computational burden at cases, SVM yields unique switching patterns otherwise not possible to be generated with carrier-based modulations.

When it comes to multilevel topologies, the modulation algorithms beyond simply synthesizing the output waveforms are also used to optimize other parameters of the VSI operation. Multi-target modulation commonly deals with either energy quality improvement or thermal optimization, or even both if the topology has the required degrees of freedom to tackle it. Fig. 2 breaks down different parameter within the energy quality and thermal optimization that can be directly target by the modulation algorithms.

The flexibility of multilevel topologies to run a multi-target modulation comes from the redundancies on the line

Fig. 2. Multi-target modulation optimization prospects.

voltage, phase voltage and switches states. For a given reference point the nearest three vectors (N3V) are usually the starting point on both voltage-level and SVM modulations [9]. From the N3V line voltage, redundancies on the phase voltage and switch states can be selected as the degrees of freedom necessary to achieve multi-target optimization. Most of the modulation strategies for multilevel topologies, however, need to primarily focus on dc-link capacitors balancing as a mandatory feature for the correct VSI operation. On the NPC-family, the dc-link balance is achieved by shaping the neutral point (NP) current with the available redundancies, thus being that the first target on a multi-target modulation. The arrow diagram in Fig. 3 exemplifies the connection among the vector domains. As a generic representation, the number of redundancies in Fig. 3 will vary in all the spaces depending on power factor, modulation index (MI), VSI topology among other design constrains.

Fig. 3. Generic spaces of line voltage, phase voltage and switch states with redundancy vectors.

As stated before, the N3V operation is the most common modulation format when it comes to line voltage selection, leaving no room for optimization in this domain. It is possible to find in the literature algorithms which will abdicate of N3V operation and therefore yield the line voltage domain with eligible redundancies to be selected during operation [9]–[11]. In [10] and [11] the line voltage vectors are used to reduce or

even eliminate the common-mode voltage (CMV) generated by the VSI. Although effective on suppressing CMV, both techniques present heavily distorted output currents, a common drawback of non-N3V operation.

Multilevel VSI, in their majority, will allow multi-target modulation using the phase voltage domain. As discussed in [6], this is possible due to the linear dependency existing on the line voltages, where different phase voltage combinations can generate the same line voltage. Considering a three-level VSI space-vector diagram, the named small vectors are formed by two different sets of phase voltages [7]. Each set will produce a different effect on the NP current and CMV. Other vectors on the diagram will have different impacts on the NP current and CMV, however the small vectors are the key ones for multi-target modulation. Still in [7], a thorough study was carried out on the use of redundant phase vectors for balancing the NP.

While the SVM approach is based on direct analysis and deployment of the redundant phase vectors, the same effects can be achieved with a carrier-based modulation (CBM) by introducing the zero sequence component to the modulating signal. Many algorithms will introduce the component in different ways: continuous compensation variable (CPWM) [12], discontinuous compensation variable (DPWM) [10], continuous modulation offset splitting the control signal in two (Double-Signal PWM – DSPWM) [13]–[15].

The last domain depicted on Fig. 3 is the switch states. In this domain, the redundancies are formed by different combinations of the power semiconductors conduction states (*on* or *off*) which generate the same phase voltage. Oppositely to the line and phase voltage redundancies, the switch states redundancies will depend directly on the VSI topology. For instance, while the NPC and TNPC topologies have no flexibility over their switching states, the ANPC can generate the O state with 4 different switch combinations. In the ANPC, the switch states are commonly used for thermal or losses optimization [8], though in [16] the EMI noise generated by the topology is modelled, presenting the impact of the 4 different switch states.

III. CM NOISE MITIGATION: APPROACH AND LIMITATIONS

The CM noise generated by a power inverter originates from the non-linear behaviour of the switching semiconductors in their rise- and fall-time during commutation. Non-idealities in the circuit, i.e., parasitic capacitances and inductances, form the path through which the noise will be conducted. For aerospace applications, the DO-160G limits the device under test (DUT) CM noise in the format of current, more precisely in dB μ A [2]. However, the CM noise generated by a VSI is usually defined by its CMV as:

$$V_{CM} = \frac{V_{AN} + V_{BN} + V_{CN}}{3}. \quad (1)$$

Since the CM current path to ground is majorly formed by capacitive elements, the dv/dt of the CMV becomes key to

mitigate the conducted emissions of a VSI according to DO-160G criteria. Fig. 4 (a) shows a usual 5 steps CMV of a three-level VSI with its harmonic content. The slope between each level of the CMV cannot be directly controlled by the modulation, being it directly related to the characteristics of the switches and their driving circuits. On the other hand, the amplitude of the signal is directly dependent on the VSI's instantaneous phase voltages which, as discussed previously, can be controlled by the modulation. Fig. 4 (b) presents a three-level VSI ideal CMV waveform achieved by the modulation scheme shown in [11].

Fig. 4. CMV waveform and harmonics content for (a) traditional three-level VSI modulation scheme and (b) complete CMV elimination.

The complete CMV elimination as presented in [11] comes at the cost of the inability to balance the dc-link capacitors through the VSI and severe harmonic distortion at the phase currents, therefore being inapplicable to the majority of the machine drive applications. A trade-off between the CM noise reduction and the output current total harmonic distortion (THD) at the VSI output is required when selecting an appropriate modulation. Three key elements on the CMV mitigation approach need to be considered:

- Overall CMV amplitude reduction.
- Number of CMV transitions reduction.
- Minimum CMV step between transitions.

Three-level topologies outperform the two-levels when it comes to switches' specifications and inverter size/weight, but at the cost of higher complexity and increased number of devices. For EMI mitigation, the trade-off also favours to three-level VSIs, as can be clearly seen on Fig. 5. The larger number of redundancies on the small vectors sets degrees of freedom for optimization on the phase voltage domain. Furthermore, for lower modulation indexes, where the zero vector is commonly deployed, it is possible to avoid the redundancies generating $\pm 1/2 V_{dc}$ CMV without impacting the THD, limiting the CMV components to the whole range of operation between $\pm 1/3 V_{dc}$ and setting a clear advantage to the two-level.

Fig. 5. Three-level space vector diagram with vectors CMV and NP current contribution.

Besides the redundancies, the vector implementation sequence is also important and is applicable to both two- and three-level topologies. The sector cut detailed in [17] presents the different effects of it on the CMV. Larger steps on the CMV will generate more CM current, therefore grouping the closest CMV levels within a switching period is detrimental for CM noise mitigation.

Despite three-level VSIs numerous advantages when compared to two-level VSIs, three-level topologies require capacitor regulation to ensure voltage balance and appropriate voltage level generation. One of the most common group of topologies, the NPCs, have the dc-link split in $n-1$ series capacitors, where n is the number of levels. For three-level NPC-family the two capacitors forming the dc-link is balanced by the current flowing through the NP. Fig. 5 presents to each line voltage on the diagram what is the equivalent phase current flowing through the NP (in module). Where phase voltage redundancies are available the sign of the NP current will be different between them, but the amplitude remains equal to the equivalent phase current as shown on the diagram. Once again, the use of the redundancies is key for the topology operation.

Considering the use of a three-level NPC-family VSI, the adopted modulation approach should tackle the following items in this priority order:

- 1) Synthesize the controller reference voltages.
- 2) Balance the dc-link capacitors.
- 3) Reduce CMV impacts.

IV. MODULATION REVIEW

A. Voltage-Level- and Vector-Based Algorithms

As a key requirement to the functionality of the NPC-family of VSIs, the dc-link voltage balance has been studied thoroughly in the literature [17]. In this document the methods presented in [12], [14] and [15] will be the baselines in the comparison to other modulation schemes focused on EMI

mitigation. Both the techniques in [12], [14] and [15] as well as other modulation schemes that will be discussed for further down in the document, will rely on the below equation for achieving dc-link voltage balance:

$$\langle I_0 \rangle_{T_s} = d_1 I_{01} + d_2 I_{02} + d_3 I_{03} \dots + d_n I_{0n}. \quad (2)$$

where: I_0 is the average current flowing to the dc-link capacitors NP during a switching period T_s , d_x is the dwell time to which the current I_{0x} will be circulating through the NP and x refers to the n different vectors which will be synthesized at the VSI output.

DSPWM modulation schemes, such as [14] and [15], tend to use a modification of (2) to represent the actual VSI phase currents and voltages (normalized to V_{dc}), while in CPWM approaches as [12] the equation is deployed in $\alpha\beta$ reference frame, or even exactly as (2) for SVM approaches. The fundamental aspect is that the essence of the analysis remains the same, as studied in [7]. For a given reference I_{0ref} , which will steer the unbalance of the dc-link capacitors towards zero, the control variable of each particular modulation scheme will use the above equation or its variations to estimate the I_0 that will match I_{0ref} .

As mentioned above, both [14] and [15] have DSPWM modulation schemes, and their approach to balance the dc-link is similar. In [14] the modulation signals are split into positive and negative parts by using the maximum and minimum phase reference voltage in the switching period and the control variable is added in the form of an offset to the positive signal. In [15], on the other hand, the control variable is applied to both the positive and negative components of the DSPWM modulating signal. Also, the saturation range of the control variable is dynamically defined depending on reference angle. On the control scheme while [14] relies on a simpler and more robust proportional gain, [15] deploys a PI controller utilized to generate the reference current that will serve to steer I_0 to the a value which balances the dc-link.

The CPWM approach presented in [12] gives a clearer vision of the limiting range for the control variable within different modulation indexes and power factor. The continuity of the zero sequence component is limited to the maximum and minimum range that prevents the modulation signal to saturate, much alike the dynamic saturation range discussed in [15]. The zero-sequence component which forces the NP current to match i_{0ref} is obtain by numerically solving the NP current equation in $\alpha\beta$ coordinates in [12].

Moving from purely dc-link voltage balance in [12], [14] and [15] to CM noise compensation, in [13] the DSPWM modulation is modified to remove the $\pm 1/3 V_{dc}$ components from the CMV. Such components, as depicted in Fig. 5, are related to the small vectors and have a redundancy equal to $\pm 1/6 V_{dc}$, being the sign between them always opposite. The $\pm 1/3 V_{dc}$ component is removed by rearranging the switching sequence of one of the phases of the VSI. The proposed modulation in [13] performs it by inverting the positive and

negative original modulating signals to an equivalent in dwell-time but reversed in sequence.

While both DSPWM and CPWM approaches deal with a continuous range in the control variable to achieve the targets set to the modulation, DPWM approaches, on the other hand, reduce the selection of the zero-sequence component to a limited number of possibilities which are discontinuous within the saturation limits. Although it may appear as a reduction on the capabilities of the modulation scheme, some DPWM techniques, as the one in [10] for instance, can actually be beneficial for CMV reduction. The approach in [10] can be split in two parts: the flat-top (FT) and the double-commutation (2C). While the FT prevents one of the VSI phases from switching, the 2C removes another commutation on the CMV, all contributing the lower conducted emissions by the VSI.

The FT is where the discontinuity of the zero-sequence component lies, and it consists on clamping one of the phases modulation signals to a point where it will not switch during a switching period (i.e., -1, 0 or +1 in normalized values in a phase-disposition). The offset applied to the clamped phase h_{N0} is equally applied to all the other phases. On a three-phase system with three different levels to clamp each phase gives a total combination of 9 different values h_{N0} can assume. In reality, saturation is avoided, and depending on the MI and other EMC constrains, as carefully analysed in [10], the possibilities for h_{N0} can be significantly reduced. This technique not only saves on the switching losses of the devices of the clamped phase as also reduces the CMV number of commutations.

The selection of h_{N0} is based on the dc-link capacitors' regulation. Following the adaptations of the (2), the NP current can be defined as [10]:

$$\langle I_0 \rangle_{T_s} = |h_{AN} + h_{N0}| I_A + |h_{BN} + h_{N0}| I_B + |h_{CN} + h_{N0}| I_C \quad (3)$$

The 2C moves the selection of the line vectors from the N3V to a configuration where two out of the three vectors will commutate two of their phase values at the same time, therefore the double-commutation. By doing so, the selection of the 2C naturally falls into vectors with the same CMV value, thus removing one CMV commutation in the switching period. For the carrier-based implementation of the 2C in [10], while one of the phases is clamped, the other two remaining phases will be compared to opposite saw-tooth carriers, one ascending and the other descending from the start of the switching period. The selection of each phase will be compared to each saw-tooth carrier can change every single switching period and it is based to remove the impact of the dead-time on the 2C [10]. At the transition between switching periods, both the ascending and descending saw-tooth will have an instantaneous change in their values, thus forcing all the phases that are not clamped to modify their states. This is the moment where the double-commutation occurs.

Moving to SVM schemes, in [18] two different approaches are presented in comparison to the traditional CPWM. The first one is the total common-mode elimination (CME), as also proposed in [11], which uses only vectors with zero V_{CM} as depicted in Fig. 5. Such approach although eliminates the CMV, has the output current heavily distorted and cannot ensure the dc-link balance. The second proposed scheme is depicted by the removal of the vectors containing the $\pm 1/3$ Vdc CMV components, similar to the DSPWM approach in [13]. The two resultants CMV presented in [18] are compared to the traditional CPWM CMV waveform. Furthermore, the authors propose a rearrange of the switching sequence of the vectors in order to avoid larger dv/dt . This last part is of key importance in order to prevent larger CM current flowing. However, in [18] the dc-link voltage balance is not addressed and by removing the vectors containing $\pm 1/3$ Vdc CMV components the regulation task becomes more challenging.

Since SVM techniques allow the free selection of the vectors according to the designer requirements, possibilities such as number of implemented vectors and vector sequence are common considerations when using SVM schemes. In [18], one of the CMV presented is a typical 4-vectors operation which relates to the triangular carrier CPWM operation [19]. It means that even within the N3V, four different phase vectors are selected inside a switching period. As can be confirmed by analysing Fig.5, to any available sub-sector in a three-level VSI space-vector diagram, at least four phase vectors will be able for form the N3V. Moreover, as the careful analysis of the sector depicted in [17] shows, 2 out of 4 sub-sectors will actually contain a total of 5 or more phase voltage redundancies. As presented before, the trade-off on adding more vectors in a switching period is the increase of the dc-link voltage controllability and improved THD against higher CM current noise and higher switching losses. On the other hand, 3-vectors operation can reduce the amount of commutation evens in the CMV and even limit the maximum CMV values to $\pm 1/3$ Vdc, as discussed in [18], but to the cost of hindering the THD and dc-link balance.

B. Modulation Impacts on the CMC Saturation

The main focus of the modulation schemes when mitigating CM noise is to have an overall CMV amplitude and number of CMV transitions reduction and minimum CMV step between transitions. Those three points, as previously discussed, will aid on reducing the high frequency content of the CM current. In several cases the noise from the higher frequencies is actually shifted to lower frequencies with a poor THD at the output currents and larger voltage ripples over the dc-link capacitors. This ultimately ends up meaning larger currents going through the common-mode choke (CMC) and, therefore, the passive will reach saturation earlier than expected. In that regard, the gains in either volume or weight obtained on the EMI filter by an efficient modulation scheme for suppressing CM noise can be actually lost on larger cores to compensate higher saturation currents.

In [20] a thorough analysis of the CMV impact over the CMC saturation is carried out. From the volt-second balance over the choke the authors correlate it to the CMV generated by the VSI and, consequently, are able to define the maximum flux density at the CMC regarding CMV levels. In this approach the geometric constants described in [21] are adapted to the volt-second use, as demonstrated in [20]. The geometric constants are effective methods to evaluate each modulation scheme's impact on the CMC size due to the noise generated at the low end of the spectrum.

C. Figures of Merit Definition

Figures of merit (FOM) are defined in pursuance of objectively understanding the performance of each modulation scheme. The two main concerning outcomes of each scheme are differently evaluated. First, at the frequency domain, the higher frequency content is assessed under the weighted sum of the harmonics that exceed the limits set by the DO-160G [2]. Fig. 6 (a) presents the CM noise generated by a generic VSI and highlights in yellow the off-limits harmonics. With the information presented in Fig. 6 (a), the weighted sum that forms the FOM can be defined as in (4). The objective of the metric is to understand at a glance the implication of different modulations on the spectrum of the CM current. At the other side of the spectrum, the low frequency impact at the CMC size is analysed by the geometric constants as defined in [20] and [21]. This FOM is obtained through the CM current peak, peak-to-peak and RMS values in the time domain. Fig. 6 (b) presents the waveform of the CM current through the CMC from which the data for the FOM can be extracted.

Fig. 6. (a) VSI CM noise with off-limits points depicted and (b) CMC common mode current.

$$S_W = \sum_{i=0}^n \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } A_i < A_{i_DO160}; \\ \frac{A_i(A_i - A_{i_DO160})}{f_i/10^6}, & \text{if } A_i \geq A_{i_DO160}. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

A full objective performance analysis of the modulation performances can be assessed by evaluating both the presented FOM together. In all the cases, the trade-off between the two FOM is complementary, to which an optimal compromising needs to be reached.

D. Simulation Overview

Several modulation schemes, among the ones described in the review, were selected for comparison regarding their performance on EMI reduction: the geometric modulation CPWM from [12] (Mod. 4), both DSPWM from [14] (Mod. 6) and [15] (Mod. 5), the DPWM in [10] both at single FT (Mod. 7) and FT-2C (Mod. 3) and the SVM approaches based on the fast SVM presented in [6] to four vectors (Mod. 1), three vectors (Mod. 2) and four vectors with sawtooth (Mod. 8). Moreover, two variations of the proposed novel modulations schemes are presented (Proposal 1 and Proposal 2).

With the output phase currents and the differential-mode (DM) and CM current flowing through the CMC, the complete analysis of each modulation can be performed. The 10 different modulation schemes were applied to the 200kW use case. The main waveforms to each scheme can be seen in Fig. 7. It is worth mentioning that since the EMI input and output filters have not been optimized to the analysis carried-out in this section. However, since the main target here is the comparative analysis between the modulation schemes, the effect of the untuned EMI filters can be disregarded once all the simulation models develop have the same parameters.

E. Modulation Effects on Conducted Emissions

Based on the input CM and the output phase currents presented in Fig. 7, the CM noise in dBuA as defined by the DO-160G can be extracted to each modulation scheme. It is nearly impossible to have a clear and objective assessment of the modulations' performances based on visual inspection of their spectrum components. In that regard the FOM described by (4) becomes fundamental for an accurate comparison. Fig. 8 is obtained after applying (4) to the CM noise spectrum.

It stands out from Fig. 8 that the Mod. 3 and the Proposal 1 have the best performance in terms of EMI among all the compared modulation schemes. Between the last two, Proposal 1 still presents a better performance than the DPWM Mod. 3 proposed in [10].

F. Modulation Effects on CMC Size

Only the EMI performance alone is not sufficient to determine the most suitable modulation for the application, as discussed before. The CMC saturation analysis is key to ensure that the select modulation will not penalize the EMI filter size. Based on the methods of [20] and [21] the geometric constants are obtained to a single CMC per modulation.

Fig. 7. Key waveforms from the 10 selected modulation schemes.

Fig. 8. FOM weighted sum comparison.

Already from Fig. 7 it was noticeable the heavily distorted input and output current produced by the DPWM techniques, especially the Mod. 3. In Fig. 9 becomes even more evident the impact that it has on the CM current and consequently on the CMC saturation.

The DPWM techniques impacts on the core saturation is evident from Fig. 9. Also, the removal of one vector in Mod. 2 scheme does not trade favourably on the lower end of the spectrum. On the other hand, modulation techniques with lower distortion on the input and output signals, as Mod. 1 for instance, will have much lower saturation currents and, consequently, smaller cores are required. In that regard, both Proposals 1 and 2 are closer to Mod. 1 sizes than Mod. 3 or even Mod. 7 in the trade-off.

By presenting the best performance on CM noise mitigation and also not compromising the size of the CMC, the Proposal

Fig. 9. Geometric constants comparison for different modulations.

1 modulation scheme is clearly the most suitable approach for the aimed application.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a review on VSI modulations and their application to CM noise mitigation. Through the paper, different modulation schemes were discussed and their impact on the CM noise assessed on a theoretical point of view. The methodology for objective evaluation of the modulations is discussed in the paper, where the metrics assessing the impact of high and low frequency harmonic content on the CMC size are established. Further on, the paper presents simulation results for 8 different literature-based modulations and 2 new proposals. From the results, it first stands out the trade-off between CM noise mitigation and output current distortion. Moreover, while few dedicated modulations can mitigate the CM noise at the high side of the frequency spectrum, the low side is severely compromised leading to early CMC saturation. Among the 10 modulations evaluated, Proposal 1 is the only one that can reach a desirable balance between effectiveness on CM noise reduction without increasing the CMC size, thus fulfilling the target of the application.

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